

A structured approach to writing a successful thesis and completing your PhD within time: the 5 chapter thesis

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Key Benefits

- Approved by reviewers / examiners
- Written in shortest time
- Uses minimum content
- Describes your research to others
- Demonstrate skill at epistemological analysis (PhD)
- Parts suitable for publication (thesis)

High Quality - Minimum Time

- For researchers and postgraduates to undertake and report high quality, well-targeted research in **minimum time** and **approved with least correction**.
- For PhD research, the target is for a thesis of around **70,000 words**, and a total time taken for research and thesis of **2.5 to 2.8 years**.
- The structure was originally developed by Perry for research in management, marketing and similar disciplines.

Research Structure

- Define *research problem*
- Find cutting-edge of information about solving the problem. Create *models* of this edge of *literature*, concepts, theories, analyses, and data in chosen *parent disciplines*
- Identify specific *research questions* that if answered will resolve the problem
- Choose *theoretical perspectives and data collection methods* to gather information to answer the *research questions*
- Report *Results* of data collection
- Explain how *new data* answers the *research questions*
- Explain how the *research problem* is resolved

Five Chapter Model

- Ch 1 - Introduction
- Ch 2 - Literature Review
- Ch 3 - Theoretical Perspective
- Ch 4 - Report of Data Collection
- Ch 5 - Conclusions & Implications
- References
- Appendices

Note: the research itself is reported from Ch 2 onwards

Ch 1 - Introduction

The *Executive Summary* with sections on:

- Background to research
- Research problem and questions
- Justification for research
- Theoretical perspective(s)
- Document outline
- Definitions
- Delimitations and key assumptions
- Conclusions

Ch 2 - Literature Review

Identify research questions that address research problem and demonstrate mastery of literature

- Introducing *Research Problem*
- Exploration of problem using **models** of parent disciplines/fields/classifications
- Development of *research questions* & hypotheses using models of immediate discipline, relevant concepts, and theories
- Summary, including list of *research questions*

Ch 3 - Theoretical perspective and data collection methods

Explain and justify the position from the research is undertaken and data collection:

- Introduce and outline roles of **theoretical perspective(s)** Ethical considerations
- Description and justification for theoretical position being adopted (ontology, epistemology, theory, methodology).
- Identify and justify **data gathering methods** for each **research question**
- Summary

Ch 4 – Results - report of data collection

Report on the data collected using the research methods and techniques described in Ch 3.

- Overview of **data collection**
- Explain theoretical and practical **differences** from plan developed in Ch 3
- Provide **patterns of data** for each research question (not raw data)
- Analyse data, and patterns, in terms of data collection methodology
- Summary

Ch 5 - Conclusions & Implications (Overview)

Ch 5 describes how the **new data**, and the **theoretical position** of Ch 3, resolves the issues described in Ch 2.

That is, Ch 5 shows how the **data collected**, the **theoretical position(s)** that were used, and the **literature reviewed**, together contribute to answering the **research questions**, and resolving the **research problem**.

Ch 5 is a significant (& long) part of the thesis.

Ch 5 - Conclusions & Implications

- Introduction
- Conclusions about each **research question**
- Conclusions about the **research problem**
- **Implications for theory**
- **Practical implications** for practice, policy, design, planning, management, marketing, and strategy
- **Limitations** of his research and conclusions
- Suggestions for **further research** in this area

References

- List all sources referred to in the thesis - and no other references.
- Use a consistent referencing structure - defined by subject area or university policy as defined in instructions for award.

Note - **Endnote or ProCite** and APA 5th style seem to work best. Further advantage is gained if the candidate uses libraries, connections, and stylesheets, notes and keywords

Appendices

Use **appendices** to present **raw data**, example analyses and derivations **outside the main thesis**.

- Use **separate appendix** for each major data source, data collection, analysis, or theory construction.
- Use appendices for **extended literature reviews** and **literature analyses that are used as data**.
- In the case of Action Research, report and **describe the Action Research project as an appendix**, so that its outcomes and observations can then be used as **data** for the main thesis.

More material

Some additional material on the 5 chapter thesis and good writing are available:

- A recent version by Chad Perry:
<http://www.tele.sunyit.edu/Thesis-Approach.pdf>
- Other papers on the 5 chapter model in
<http://www.love.com.au/PublicationsTLminisite/Publications.htm>
- Emerald Insight:
<http://iris.emeraldinsight.com/vl=6189499/cl=103/nw=1/rpsv/literaticlub/authors.htm>